

LintedData

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Poster

<https://elib.dlr.de/223803/>

Repository

<https://gitlab.com/dlr-dw/linteddata/>

🎯 Goals

- ▶ Run RDF and OWL quality checks automatically
- ▶ Easy setup and automation

📄 What is LintedData?

LintedData is a linter for RDF. It is a CLI tool, intended for the use in CI/CD pipelines, that checks for common mistakes and compliance to best practices in RDF graphs. The scope of LintedData is domain-independent constraints on RDF graphs, aiming to complement technologies like SHACL or ShEx for domain-specific constraints.

🔗 Use in GitLab CI Pipelines

```
linted-data:
  stage: test
  image: dlr-dw/linteddata:latest
  script:
    - LintedData <inputFile> --junit linted-data.xml
  artifacts:
    reports:
      junit: linted-data.xml
```

📄 Results View in GitLab

🔧 Configuration

LintedData is intended to only execute meaningful checks automatically, but can be configured using a simple YAML configuration file:

```
checks:
  RDF: false # deactivated scope
  RDFS: true # activated scope
  OWL: # activated scope
  SelfInversePropertyCheck: false # deactivated check
  OntologyIriOboConformanceCheck: true # activated check
  MissingLicenseForOntologyCheck: # activated check
  parameters: # configuration of a check
    permittedLicenses:
      - https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/
      - https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
```

The configuration YAML is provided as CLI parameter:

```
LintedData <inputFile> --config <configFile>
```

🔗 Features

- ▶ 60+ checks implemented
- ▶ Docker image and executable JAR available
- ▶ JUnit XML and Markdown result export

🔗 Use in GitHub CI Pipelines

```
jobs:
  linted-data:
    runs-on: ubuntu-latest
    container: dlr-dw/linteddata:latest
    steps:
      - name: Checkout Project
        uses: actions/checkout@v6
      - name: Check with LintedData
        run: LintedData <inputFile> --markdown linted-data.md
      - name: Add LintedData results to job summary
        if: ${{ !cancelled() }}
        run: head -qc1023k linted-data.md >> $GITHUB_STEP_SUMMARY
```

🔍 What does LintedData check?

- ▶ Ontology Pitfalls Catalogue coverage
- ▶ OBO Foundry ontology principles support
- ▶ Checks for 4 scopes
 - ▶ **RDF**, for example
 - ▶ DifferentNamingConventionsCheck
 - ▶ LeadingOrTrailingSpaceCheck
 - ▶ **RDFS**, for example
 - ▶ MissingLabelCheck
 - ▶ MultipleRangesCheck
 - ▶ **OWL**, for example
 - ▶ CycleInClassHierarchyCheck
 - ▶ VersionIriExistenceCheck
 - ▶ **BFO**, for example
 - ▶ ClassNotInBfoHierarchyCheck
 - ▶ NotReusedRelationsOntologyPropertyCheck

🔗 How to extend LintedData?

LintedData is easy to extend with additional checks:

- ▶ Write Java Check Class providing descriptions
- ▶ Register Java Check Class
- ▶ Write SPARQL Check Query
- ▶ Write Java Unit Test Class

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